

Comparing User Perspectives In a Virtual Reality Cultural Heritage Environment

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Abstract. Virtual reality enables the creation of personalized users experiences that put together people of different cultures and ethnicity. We consider a novel concept of virtual reality innovation in museums, which is cognitively grounded, and based on data and their semantics, to enable users to share their experiences, as well as to assume the perspective of other users, with the ultimate goal of increasing social cohesion. The implementation of this scenario requires an autonomous artificial system capable to detect emotions and values from a dialogue involving museum visitors who express their personal point of view, listen to the point of view of other visitors, and assume others' perspectives.

An important feature of this system is the ability of detecting similarity and dissimilarity between users' perspectives expressed by speech when exposed to artworks. This aids in defining an effective strategy for sharing diverse user perspectives for increasing social cohesion. Moreover, it enables an unbiased quantification of the success of the interaction in terms of change in the user perspective. Based on results from previous work, we employ the Ekman emotion model and Haidt moral value model to detect emotional and moral value profiles from user descriptions of artworks. We propose a novel method for measuring the similarity between user perspectives by comparing emotional and moral value profiles. Our results show that the employment of unsupervised text classification models is a promising research direction for this task.

Keywords: Text similarity · Emotion detection · Moral value detection · Virtual reality.

1 Introduction

Virtual Reality (VR) is an innovative technology that, by isolating the perceptive channels of users, makes them feel immersed in a virtual environment, through the sensations of virtual embodiment [32]. Its effectiveness is mainly due to its imaginative power, which allows users to experience situations as they

were real [20]. This sensation of reality is given by the system’s ability to process the information received, and to offer visual and sound feedback in real time [33]. Today VR is applied in many domains related to cognitive sciences, including social technology, which facilitates interactions by promoting the psychological well-being of people in social contexts. As a countermeasure, as a part of a wider project⁴, which aims to ensure social cohesion, participation and inclusion through cultural engagement, we use the virtual reality technology to build an innovative system, in which users are subjected to the Interpretation-Reflection Loop (IRL) [7] in an immersive environment that makes them share their personal interpretations with others, listen to others’ interpretations given by different people, and take another point of view through virtual embodiment. In this sense we are implementing a system able to work through continuous communication between its constituent parts, i.e., between the VR interface jointly with an external server capable of detecting emotions and moral values from the user’s speech, and the user itself. The system builds a specific avatar for each user, based on their personal characteristics such as age, gender and nationality; subsequently, following the user’s first interpretation, the external server detects emotions and moral values to select an appropriate avatar that will interact with the user. All users’ interpretations are recorded and associated with specific avatars. These data are saved in an external dataset that the server can access for further reuse.

An essential feature of the described system is the ability of quantifying the similarity between user perspectives. For instance, presenting perspectives that are different from their ones to users can make them think about their standpoint and encourage them to adopt a wider perspective, ultimately increasing social cohesion. The task can also be useful for comparing perspectives of a user at two different points in time, e.g. before and after an interaction, to quantify the propensity of people to change their point of view under certain circumstances (e.g. when impersonating an avatar with a different standpoint). Considering the large volume of data to process and the necessity of performing the task on-line and autonomously, it is essential that the system is able to reason with user perspectives and quantify their similarity.

We adopt a novel method to quantify the similarity between user perspectives through emotional and moral values lenses [19]. We leverage on text classifiers to extract emotional profiles and moral value profiles from text obtained by speech-to-text. We then compare profiles from different speeches by means of cosine similarity. To evaluate our method we collected data from our VR prototype, obtaining a total of 396 interpretations on 6 works of art associated to 6 avatars. We compared some state-of-the-art supervised and unsupervised classifiers based on Transformers and adopt the top-performing one for computing the similarity between perspectives.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Next, we present some background on social and technological aspects of our work (Sect. 2). In section 3

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we present our VR scenario that we use for data collection. Section 4 presents our method for evaluating and comparing user perspectives. We report our results in section 5 and then conclude in section 6.

2 Background

We provide some background on social (Sect. 2.1) and technological (Sect. 2.2) aspects related to this work. First, we briefly overview recent work on social cohesion, which motivates the importance of implementing suitable strategies and developing effective tools for favouring it. Second, we discuss the reference models we employ and evaluate for automatically detecting emotions and moral values evoked by people’s speech. We also describe state-of-the-art metrics for computing the semantic similarity between natural language sentences, which we employ as a starting point for our method.

2.1 Improving Social Cohesion

In the field of cognitive science, social cohesion represents an important topic that needs to be investigated since, as shown in recent studies [17, 16, 29, 28], the lack of social cohesion, which increases social isolation, can have a strong impact on people’s health, impacting life expectancy and increasing the risk of death, as well as the risk of developing dementia. Previous studies have shown that virtual embodiment enables empathetic sharing of personal experiences that boosts social inclusion [5, 32] as well as a reduction of prejudices towards different people [35]. For instance, Slater et al. [31] have shown that adopting another point of view allows the user to be more sensitive to violent behavior, leading to a reduction in racial aggression [18] and a decrease in child maltreatment [14]. In this line, in our previous work (Lucifora et al., under revision), we used an ecological paradigm in virtual reality to promote social cohesion through the virtual embodiment. Our results show that the percentages of people who change their interpretation (totally or partially) when they embody the avatar are equal to or greater than the ones who do not change their interpretation at all (Chi square between subjects p-level 0.018; Chi-square within subjects group n.1 p-level 0.007; Chi-square within subjects group n.2 p-level 0.016).

2.2 Reference models

Previous work on moral values and emotions detection focuses on machine learning techniques and quantitative or semantic text document analysis [22, 1, 26, 23].

For the purposes of our study, we selected three different methods based on natural language models to classify the emotional and moral perspective of users based on their natural language descriptions of artworks⁵. The first

⁵ all methods take as input text documents, which can be generated by a speech-to-text tool

is based on Asprino et al. [4], which employs a zero-shot classification in an unsupervised way, drawing inspiration from Yin et al. [36]. This approach is based on the use of a model trained for a natural language inference (NLI) task, where a *premise* is determined whether or not it entails a *hypothesis*. Starting from the input text document as a premise, the system recognizes if one or more taxonomic labels, provided as hypotheses, are semantically coherent with the input. The advantage of this method is that it does not require training on an annotated dataset and hence it is directly applicable in our scenario, where we cannot rely on a large annotated dataset. We evaluate two additional supervised BERT-based machine learning models trained on available datasets. Both systems take textual data as input to perform a multi-class classification task based on Ekman’s taxonomy. [24, 15]. The former is trained on a set of tweets, while the latter has a greater heterogeneity, as it is fine-tuned on a large number of different sources such as Twitter, Reddit, student self-assessments and television dialogue expressions. Both these methods suffer from the data shift problem, i.e. their performances degrade when applied to data with different characteristics than the training set [34].

To measure the change of user perspective and compare perspectives of different users, we consider as a baseline a state-of-the-art technique for semantic similarity among text documents, consisting on computing a vector representation of each text document and compare them by means of cosine similarity. We employ Sentence-BERT [27] for computing the text representation. Sentence-BERT is a variant of the pre-trained BERT model [10] that generates semantically significant sentence embeddings using siamese and triplet network structures. The limit of this method in our scenario is that it considers the overall semantic similarity and cannot focus on a specific lens (emotional or value) to compare perspectives.

3 Data Collection

We applied an ecological paradigm in VR, made up by a helmet of virtual reality (Oculus Quest 2), equipped with a headphone that provides 3D audio effects, and an immersive and realistic virtual museum based on Blue Dot Studios-Art Gallery, developed with Unity Engine 3D 2020.3.33 as software. Inside the virtual museum, we included some artworks of the Modern Art Gallery in Turin (Italy) and avatars, which we built using Ready-player.me and Mixamo.com for the animations. We built 27 avatars, representative of the world population categorized by age, gender, and nationality (Figure 1). We tested 44 Italian subjects, recording 396 verbal interpretations (in Italian language) on 6 works of art, related to 6 avatars. We divided our sample into two experimental groups (N=22) in order to balance our stimuli in relation to the main characteristics of the avatars and art movements. We have prepared an interview based on four questions based on widely used theories for emotions [11] and moral values [13]. Two questions are related to the user’s feeling (Q1 ”How does this work of art make you feel?”; Q2 ”What moral value does this work of art inspire you?”),

while two questions are related to the specific categorization of emotions and values (Q3 "Among these emotions (Ekman’s model) which do you think the work of art arouses?"; Q4 "Of these values (Haidt’s model) which one do you think the work of art arouses?"). Our procedure is based on a 4-step timeline: At time 0 the user provides its personal interpretation of the work, based on an interview given by the researcher. At time 1 the user is invited to listen to the (verbally expressed) interpretation provided by the avatar who shares the scene with him. At time 2, users give their personal reflection, discussing their interpretations against those of the avatar. No specific questions are asked here. At the last time (time 3), the user is invited to respond again to the structured interview, given by the researcher, but this time users take the role of the avatar through virtual embodiment. We have recorded 3 verbal interpretations (time 0, time 2, time 3) for each participant.

4 Comparing Perspectives by Emotion and Moral Value Classification

In order to detect the emotions and moral values from human-avatar dialogues, we analyzed the answers to Q1 and Q2 at time 0 and time 3, plus the free reflection at time 2, using the supervised and unsupervised AI systems for natural language understanding discussed in Sect. 2.2. Following Asprino et al.[4], we apply a pre-trained Natural Language Inference system as ready-made zero-shot sequence classifier (namely NLI-based). We use the framework to categorize emotions and moral values, developing two different system configurations based respectively on the taxonomies of Ekman and Haidt. We compared the results with two distinct BERT-based supervised models for emotion detection: E-BERTweet [24] and E-DistilRoBERTa [15] trained on annotated benchmark data [30, 9, 8, 25, 21, 3].

We propose a novel method to determine how emotionally and morally comparable the text documents are. Specifically, we compare the answers to Q1 and Q2 at time 0 and time 3 to understand whether the users changed their perspective after the virtual embodiment (time 3) with respect to their first interpretation of the artwork (time 0). Since to the best of our knowledge there is no approach available to measure the similarity of perspective through an emotional and/or value lens, we consider as a baseline the cosine similarity between Sentence-BERT text representations (Sect. 2.2).

Our approach considers the output function of the (emotion or moral value) classifier, typically a probability distribution over the set of classes computed by a softmax normalization function, of each text document and compute their cosine similarity. Specifically:

$$emotional_similarity(t_1, t_2) = \frac{\mathbf{f}_e(t_1) \cdot \mathbf{f}_e(t_2)}{\|\mathbf{f}_e(t_1)\| \|\mathbf{f}_e(t_2)\|} \quad (1)$$

$$value_similarity(t_1, t_2) = \frac{\mathbf{f}_v(t_1) \cdot \mathbf{f}_v(t_2)}{\|\mathbf{f}_v(t_1)\| \|\mathbf{f}_v(t_2)\|} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_e(t)$ and $\mathbf{f}_v(t)$ are the output vectors of the emotional and value classifiers on text t , respectively; \cdot is the dot product between vectors and $\|\mathbf{x}\|$ is the 2-norm of vector \mathbf{x} .

The result is a value between 0 and 1, where 0 represent completely different perspectives, while 1 represent perfectly coincident perspectives. The method can be applied even when the output does not represent a probability distribution, provided that it is given as a vector of N non-negative values, where N is the number of classes. In our experiments (Sect. 5) we consider the output of the zero-shot NLI-based emotion and moral value classifiers normalized by softmax.

5 Results and Evaluation

We consider two basic experimental frameworks dealing with emotional and value-based detection and similarity in text, respectively. Next we describe the setup and results of detection, then we discuss the results concerning similarity.

Emotion and moral detection For the moral and emotion classification we considered the answers to questions Q1 and Q2 at time 0 (t0), time 2 (t2) and time 3 (t3) for both experimental groups (see Sect. 3) and divided our sample in three categories, that are: (i) *irrelevant* answers, which do not contain any emotions or moral values; (ii) *incoherent* answers, which contain emotions incompatible with their annotations; (iii) *relevant* (and coherent) answers, which express and annotate clear emotions or moral values. We consider the user’s annotations of emotions and moral values (answers to questions Q3 and Q4, respectively) as the ground truth and compare the system’s predictions with them to measure performances. For the emotion classification task we compare the unsupervised NLI-based model [4], and the supervised E-BERTeet [24] and E-DistilRoBERTa [15] models, introduced in Sect. 2.2. We adopt the unsupervised NLI-based [4] method for detecting moral values.

We report the results in terms of weighted F1-score. We compute the outcomes considering six basic emotions and six value dimensions, respectively. The results show that the models are able to detect the emotions and values from relevant (and coherent) answers with significant accuracy, for any step (Table 1 and Table 2). As expected, the performances degrade for irrelevant and incoherent answers, since the user annotations are not representative of the emotions and moral values expressed in the free answer.

With the exception of time t0 of the second trial, the NLI-based model [4] performs noticeably better in both the first and second group for the emotion detection task. In this scenario, the F1-score ranges from 0.56 to 0.72. For the task of identifying moral values the F1 score fluctuates between 32% and 49% on relevant answers. Considering the difficulty of the task, because of subjectivity and ambiguity of moral values expressed in natural language statements, we consider this result promising.

Table 1: Emotion detection results for the unsupervised zero-shot model (NLI-based) and supervised BERT-based models (E-BERTweet and E-DistilRoBERTa) in terms of weighted F1-score. In relevant (and coherent) answers, NLI-based outperforms supervised methods (which have been trained on third-part datasets). As expected, the F1-score is low for irrelevant and incoherent answers since the users’ annotations do not represent the real emotions expressed in the free answers.

Category	Model	Group n. 1			Group n. 2		
		t0	t2	t3	t0	t2	t3
Relevant	NLI-based	.72	.62	.70	.56	.56	.47
	E-BERTweet	.56	.34	.47	.36	.36	.22
	E-DistilRoBERTa	.67	.48	.61	.66	.55	.47
Irrelevant	NLI-based	.26	.05	.26	.11	.20	.09
	E-BERTweet	.11	.01	.01	.42	.10	.04
	E-DistilRoBERTa	.44	.01	.06	.36	.01	.04
Incoherent	NLI-based	.19	.18	.13	.06	.25	.20
	E-BERTweet	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
	E-DistilRoBERTa	.00	.23	.22	.08	.00	.00

Table 2: Moral value detection results for the unsupervised NLI-based zero-shot model in terms of weighted F1-score. As for the emotion detection case, the F1-score is low for irrelevant and incoherent answers since the users’ annotations do not represent the real moral values expressed in the free answers.

Category	Group n. 1			Group n. 2		
	t0	t2	t3	t0	t2	t3
Relevant	.48	.49	.35	.38	.32	.29
Irrelevant	.09	.30	.42	.18	.30	.33
Incoherent	.27	.30	.33	.18	.32	.19

Emotional and moral similarity To evaluate the emotional and moral similarity scores, we consider the portion of cases of our sample that are consistent and relevant with user annotations. Two annotators evaluated the statements given at time 0 and time 3 to determine whether there is a change in the user’s emotional and moral perspective. Annotators specifically highlighted sentences that expressed distinctions with a “yes” (corresponding to non similar perspectives) and coherent text with a “no” (corresponding to similar perspectives). We compare the scores with the conforming annotations to see how well our system can discern between similar and dissimilar phrases in terms of their moral and emotional content.

We use the Area Under the Curve (AUC) measure to evaluate the performances of our emotional and moral similarity technique. Results are reported in table 3. The outcomes show that our tool consistently produces AUC comparable or higher than the reference BERT-based semantic similarity system Sentence-BERT [27] discussed in section 2.2. We obtained an AUC score of 81% and 70% for emotional and moral semantic similarity, respectively.

Table 3: AUC of the similarity metrics for predicting a change in perspective. We evaluate emotional, moral, and semantic similarity for coherent statements between answers at time 0 and time 3.

Task	Emotional Similarity	Moral Similarity	SBert	Support
Emotional validation	0,81		0,81	25
Moral validation		0,70	0,66	19

In summary, NLI-based emotion and moral detection systems show significant performances when the user annotation is coherent with the free description. Furthermore, the NLI model outcomes for the emotion detection task are superior to those of supervised systems trained on third-part datasets. This confirms the versatility of unsupervised architectures in out-of-domain tasks. The results obtained from the emotional and moral similarity system show an overall positive trend in capturing the emotional and value nuances of sentences.

6 Conclusion

In order to improve social cohesion, we are implementing an automated integration of VR and AI, to deploy perspective taking into museums with only an update of VR environment objects, works of art, and user metadata. To this end, we have recorded a total of 396 verbal interpretations from 44 subjects, using an experimental procedure based on a 4-step workflow, employed on an immersive VR system. Our results lead to two important considerations. The first one is related to the utility of VR interface to promote social cohesion. In this sense, in line with recent literature [2], our results show that virtual embodiment is able

to increase prosocial behavior and arouse empathy among users. Our data relating to the higher number of empathic people compared to non-empathic people during virtual embodiment, confirms previous studies that show that the first perspective in an immersive virtual reality leads to a strong feeling of embodiment towards an artificial body [6], which on its turn allows users to be more empathetic in relation to the feeling of other people [12]. The second result of our research is related to the use of automatic language inference systems. Our results show that zero-shot learning for transformers is able to detect emotions expressed and moral values evocated by the personal interpretation of artworks. Furthermore, the method we have introduced for determining the degree of emotional and moral coherence between two statements illustrates how it is possible to compare sentences from this specific point of view.

In conclusion, our results point to the feasibility of building an innovative VR system based on data semantics, as a valid tool to sensitize people to other interpretations, improving social cohesion through virtual embodiment.

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